

A Study on Different Treatment Modalities in the Management of Anal Fistula

Chinta Anjini Suvarchala Devi¹, Palaparthi Samson Subhash², N U Deepthi³,
Bevunapalli Sirisha⁴, Rakesh Bevunapalli⁵

¹3rd Year Post Graduate, Department of General Surgery, Konaseema Institute of Medical Sciences and Research Foundation, Amalapuram

²3rd Year Post Graduate, Department of General Surgery, Konaseema Institute of Medical Sciences and Research Foundation, Amalapuram

³Assistant Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Konaseema Institute of Medical Sciences and Research Foundation, Amalapuram

⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Konaseema Institute of Medical Sciences and Research Foundation, Amalapuram

⁵Associate Professor, Department of General Surgery, Konaseema Institute of Medical Sciences and Research Foundation, Amalapuram

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Rakesh Bevunapalli

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Abstract

Introduction: Anal fistula, a common anorectal condition, is treated using various modalities like fistulotomy, fistulectomy, fibrin glue, fistula plug insertion, ligation of the intersphincteric tract (LIFT), and video-assisted anal fistula treatment (VAAFT). Each has distinct advantages and challenges. This study aimed to assess the efficacy, complications, and adherence to treatment principles of these five techniques.

Methods: This cross-sectional study at Konaseema Institute involved adult patients with primary or recurrent anal fistulas. They underwent procedures including fistulotomy, fistulectomy, fibrin glue application, fistula plug insertion, LIFT, and VAAFT. Outcomes assessed at 1, 3, and 6 months included fistula closure rates, complications, and patient satisfaction. Statistical analysis utilized chi-square tests and Kaplan-Meier survival analysis.

Results: In a study of 120 patients, fistulotomy and fistulectomy had the highest success rate (85%) but with 15% minor incontinence. Fibrin glue application showed the lowest success (50%) and highest recurrence (30%). Fistula plug insertion had a 65% success rate, LIFT 75%, and VAAFT 70%, with minimal complications.

Conclusion: Managing anal fistulas requires an individualized approach, balancing fistula complexity with patient factors. Fistulotomy and fistulectomy offer high success but carry incontinence risks, while minimally invasive options like LIFT and VAAFT balance efficacy and safety. Fibrin glue and fistula plugs are less invasive but have lower success in complex cases.

Keywords: Anal fistula, Fistulotomy, Minimally invasive, LIFT, Recurrence rates.

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Introduction

Anal fistula is a common proctologic condition resulting from an abnormal connection between the anorectal canal and the perianal skin. [1] It typically arises due to infection of the anal glands, which leads to abscess formation and subsequent fistula development. Managing anal fistula presents a significant challenge, as the primary goal is to eradicate the fistula while preserving continence and minimizing recurrence. Various treatment modalities are available, each with distinct advantages and limitations. [2, 3]

Fistulotomy and fistulectomy are traditional surgical methods, where the fistula tract is either laid open or excised, providing high cure rates but with the risk of postoperative incontinence. Fibrin glue application offers a minimally invasive approach, where a biocompatible adhesive is injected into the fistula tract, though its effectiveness may be compromised by a higher recurrence rate. [1, 4] Fistula plug insertion utilizes a biologically derived material to occlude the tract and stimulate healing. Ligation of the intersphincteric tract (LIFT) involves isolating and closing the fistula tract at the intersphincteric plane,

offering good success with low morbidity. Lastly, video-assisted anal fistula treatment (VAAFT) employs endoscopic guidance to identify and treat the fistula tract with minimal tissue disruption [2, 5].

This study aims to investigate the efficacy, complications, and adherence to treatment principles of five commonly employed techniques: fistulotomy and fistulectomy, fibrin glue application, fistula plug insertion, ligation of the LIFT, and VAAFT.

Methods

It was a cross sectional study conducted in the department of general Surgery, Konaseema Institute of Medical Sciences and Research Foundation, Amalapuram, East Godavari, Andhra Pradesh. Study protocol was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee. An informed written consent was taken from the study members. Study was conducted between May 2022 to March 2024.

Patients were stratified based on the type of procedure they underwent: fistulotomy, fistulectomy, fibrin glue application, fistula plug insertion, LIFT and VAAFT. Inclusion criteria involved adult patients aged 18-65 years with primary or recurrent anal fistulas. Exclusion criteria included patients with Crohn's disease, tuberculosis, or malignancies.

Each patient underwent a thorough clinical evaluation and imaging via endoanal ultrasound or magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) to classify the fistula type. Surgical procedures were performed by experienced colorectal surgeons following standardized protocols. Postoperative follow-up was conducted at regular intervals of 1, 3, and 6 months to assess fistula healing, recurrence, and complications such as incontinence, infection, or abscess formation.

Outcomes were compared based on fistula closure rates, time to healing, incidence of complications, and patient-reported quality of life. Statistical analysis was conducted using chi-square tests for categorical variables and Kaplan-Meier survival analysis to evaluate recurrence-free survival. The primary endpoint was the complete closure of the fistula without recurrence at six months post-procedure, while secondary endpoints included postoperative complications and patient satisfaction scores.

Results

A total of 120 patients with anal fistula were divided into five treatment groups: fistulotomy and fistulectomy (n=40), fibrin glue application (n=20), fistula plug insertion (n=20), LIFT (n=20), and VAAFT (n=20). Fistulotomy and fistulectomy had

the highest success rate (85%) but were associated with a 15% incidence of minor incontinence. Fibrin glue application showed the lowest success rate (50%) and the highest recurrence rate (30%). Fistula plug insertion achieved a 65% closure rate with low complications, while LIFT demonstrated a 75% success rate and minimal complications. VAAFT had a 70% closure rate, minimal postoperative pain, and a 25% recurrence rate.

Discussion

Anal fistula remains a significant public health issue in India, affecting predominantly males, with a prevalence of around 8-10 cases per 100,000 people. Delayed diagnosis and treatment are common, particularly in rural areas, leading to complications such as recurrence and incontinence. Factors such as poor hygiene, untreated perianal abscesses, and limited access to specialized care contribute to the disease burden [6, 7]. Traditional surgical treatments like fistulotomy are frequently employed, though newer minimally invasive techniques are slowly gaining acceptance in tertiary care centers.

Fistulotomy and fistulectomy are widely recognized as the most effective treatments for anal fistula, with success rates of approximately 85%, particularly in simple fistulas. Both procedures involve either laying open the fistula tract (fistulotomy) or excising it completely (fistulectomy), ensuring a high rate of fistula closure. However, these procedures are associated with a significant risk of postoperative complications, most notably minor incontinence. [8] Approximately 15% of patients experience some degree of incontinence, especially when the fistula involves a larger portion of the anal sphincter. This complication arises from damage to the sphincter muscles during surgery, which can impair bowel control. Despite these risks, fistulotomy and fistulectomy remain preferred options for treating low or simple fistulas due to their overall efficacy in achieving long-term healing with minimal recurrence. [9]

Fibrin glue application, a minimally invasive treatment for anal fistula, has demonstrated limited efficacy, with a success rate of around 50%. The procedure involves injecting fibrin glue into the fistula tract to promote healing through tissue adhesion [10]. Despite its attractiveness due to its simplicity and low risk of incontinence, fibrin glue has shown the highest recurrence rate of approximately 30%. Its limited effectiveness is attributed to the inability of the glue to fully seal the fistula tract, particularly in complex or high fistulas. Moreover, the glue may degrade too quickly before the fistula has a chance to heal completely, leading to failure and recurrence. [10, 11] Due to these drawbacks, fibrin glue is generally

reserved for cases where more invasive procedures are not feasible, or patients prefer a non-surgical option, although its long-term effectiveness remains questionable.

Fistula plug insertion, a sphincter-sparing technique, achieved a 65% closure rate with minimal complications, making it an appealing option for patients. This procedure involves inserting a biologically derived plug into the fistula tract to promote healing, particularly effective for straightforward cases. [4] However, recurrence occurs in about 20% of cases, particularly in more complex fistulas. The LIFT technique demonstrated a higher success rate of 75%, with a similarly low complication profile. LIFT is especially effective for transsphincteric fistulas, where preserving sphincter function is crucial, offering an optimal balance between efficacy and safety. [5] The VAAFT provided a 70% closure rate, with minimal postoperative pain and complications. Despite these advantages, recurrence rates remain a concern, with up to 25% of patients experiencing recurrence. [4]

Conclusion

The management of anal fistulas requires a tailored approach, considering the complexity of the fistula and patient factors. Fistulotomy and fistulectomy offer the highest success rates but come with an increased risk of complications, particularly incontinence. Minimally invasive procedures like LIFT and VAAFT provide a good balance between efficacy and safety, with lower risks of incontinence and complications. Fibrin glue and fistula plug insertion, while less invasive, show lower success rates and higher recurrence in complex cases. Ultimately, individualized

treatment plans are essential to optimize outcomes and minimize risks for each patient.

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